

1 **Realities of the consortium approach in Science: Sustainable enzymatic production of C1** 2 **chemicals from carbon dioxide**

3 Andrea Rodil,^{a,b} Ingemar von Ossowski,^b Mari Nyysönen,^c Yufang Tian,^b Marleen Hallamaa,^a Jan Deska,^a
4 Malin Bomberg^c and Silvan Scheller^b

5
6 ^a University of Helsinki, Department of Chemistry, A. I. Virtasen aukio 1, 00560 Helsinki, Finland

7 ^b Aalto University, Department of Bioproducts and Biosystems, School of Chemical Engineering,
8 Kemistintie 1, 02150 Espoo, Finland

9 ^c VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Espoo, Finland

10

11 **Abstract**

12 Research at the frontiers of science is getting increasingly specialised. At the same time, major
13 global challenges require the cooperation and innovation of different research fields. One
14 solution for enhancing scientific discovery and innovation within this landscape is to form
15 research consortia that bring together expertise from different disciplines. Such
16 multidisciplinary efforts are also highly recognized and increasingly enforced by funding
17 agencies. Within this landscape, we established a research consortium consisting of three
18 partners to explore environmental acid-tolerant formate dehydrogenases as novel biocatalysts
19 for formic acid production from CO₂. Taking our ambitious project on biocatalytic CO₂
20 valorisation as a case study, we reflect on the realities of forming a research consortium,
21 highlighting some of the related theoretical and technical issues, as well as its intrinsic positive
22 and valuable nourishing effect on researchers. Finally, we offer some constructive criticism
23 and practical advice to other scientists willing to embark on complex scientific projects through
24 collaborations.

25

26 **1. Introduction**

27 One of the main virtues, and problems, of modern science is specialisation. Whilst the
28 scientific community is blessed to have many talented researchers able to solve wide-spread
29 and niche problems alike, the tendency is for those researchers to be highly specialised in their
30 fields. This circumstance is equally a catalyst for the progress of science and the inhibitor that
31 stalls the speed of discovery. Nowadays, our community faces increasingly complex
32 challenges, and these challenges will only be resolved by the joint hard work of highly

33 specialised scientists, together. Funding bodies and governmental programmes begin to see the
34 value of multidisciplinary work, and researchers are constantly being encouraged to form
35 partnerships.

36 One of the most prominent threats to humanity is global warming. The current
37 worldwide carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from fossil fuel use remain excessive and the
38 natural capacity for photosynthetic CO₂ assimilation continues to be outstripped.¹⁻⁵ Thus, the
39 prospect of CO₂ utilisation will not only help achieve more tolerable atmospheric CO₂ levels,
40 but it will provide a carbon source that is large enough to substitute fossil carbon sources. In
41 this quest to access CO₂ as a carbon source, it is crucial that we get inspiration from nature.
42 The last decade has seen an active development on the field of synthetic biology, with cutting-
43 edge technologies designed to biocatalytically convert CO₂ emissions into high value-added
44 chemical products such as formic acid (HCOOH).^{6,7} Formic acid can be further transformed
45 into high-value chemicals.^{8,9}

46 Soon, we encountered our first challenge: specialisation. From a chemist's perspective,
47 biocatalytic research is often constrained in terms of commercial availability, considerably
48 limiting the scope of experimentation, and failing to adequately answer key questions or deliver
49 novel solutions and data. Although the situation can be improved by producing a broader
50 collection of enzymatic species, the necessary scientific skills, know-how, and infrastructure
51 do not always coexist within a purely chemistry-based research group. At the same time, from
52 the biologist's perspective, the idea of taking formic acid and being able to obtain other
53 molecules might seem unsurpassable. As a solution, entering into a formal collaborative
54 partnership, with researchers from various other academic and technical disciplines, is a proven
55 approach for addressing any theoretical or research shortcomings frequently associated with a
56 highly ambitious and complex project and highly specialised researchers.

57 In this perspective article, we consider the benefits and limitations of forming a
58 consortium, starting with the fact that funding bodies and research agencies are beginning to
59 see the value of this kind of multidisciplinary work, and researchers are constantly being
60 encouraged to form partnerships. In our view, we understood that taking this approach would
61 carry a high degree of conceptual risk, as our proposed project involved highly ambitious and
62 challenging research with a good deal of scientific uncertainty and unpredictability. Even so,
63 by pursuing this 'high risk-high gain' strategy, both researchers and funding agencies alike,
64 certainly expected that the anticipated outcome would clearly outweigh the element of risk and
65 possible failure of the research. Take our project as a case study.

66

67 2. Research description and objectives

68 In 2019, the Research Council of Finland (formerly the Academy of Finland) issued a
69 special call aimed at proposals that could strengthen Finnish scientific competence and
70 competitiveness in the utilisation of green chemistry technologies for industrial manufacturing
71 of products from captured CO₂ emissions.¹⁰ As scientists interested on the topic, we prepared
72 a proposal, and thus, ‘ExtremoForm: Extremophile Microorganisms as a Source of Highly
73 Productive Enzymes for CO₂ Reduction to Formic Acid and Other C1 Fuels and Platform
74 Chemicals’ was born. With academic and scientific partners from the VTT Technical Research
75 Centre of Finland Ltd., Aalto University, and the University of Helsinki; three disciplines were
76 involved: environmental metagenomics, expression of enzymes and chemical catalysis (Fig.
77 1).

78
79 **Fig. 1** In ExtremoForm, each consortium participant brought their unique expertise and
80 resources to the research: environmental genomics and microbial sampling from extreme
81 habitats, anaerobic biochemistry and recombinant protein expression, and molecular
82 characterisation of enzymes through enzyme design and engineering for applied biocatalysis
83 and organic synthesis; ideally - to maximise outcomes - the cycle can then be perfected and
84 re-started with the help of computational tools and artificial intelligence learning.

85 In particular, our main collective aim was to procure a selection of enzymes - formate
86 dehydrogenases (FDHs) - that are acid-tolerant and active in low temperature conditions, and
87 with a strong preference for CO₂ reductase catalysis. These novel FDHs represent a sustainable
88 green alternative, because they rely on non-toxic molybdenum and tungsten, instead of toxic
89 transition metals such as rhodium that are typically used by classical chemical catalysts. Via
90 enzymatic promiscuity, we focused on the direct production of formic acid for the
91 environmentally friendly generation of high value-added chemicals and fuels. Notably, we
92 focus on formic acid, and not formate, to avoid the problem of having to provide a counter ion
93 for each formate produced. In addition, formic acid can be used to address the problematic
94 transport and storage of hydrogen (H₂) for the renewable energy industry.

95 To advance this outcome, our five strategic targets were laid out as follows: (i) to screen
96 and uncover metallo-FDH biocatalysts that efficiently reduce CO₂ to formic acid at zero degree
97 temperatures and under extremely acidic conditions (pH < 3), (ii) to attain a fundamental
98 understanding of the molecular mechanisms behind the low temperature activity and high acid
99 stability of the FDH biocatalysts, (iii) to improve the performance of the FDH biocatalysts by
100 using a combination of directed evolution and semi-rational protein engineering and design,
101 (iv) to characterise the properties of the FDH biocatalysts by applying the same conventional
102 methods used for chemical catalysts, and (v) to broaden the reaction specificity of the existing
103 FDH biocatalysts for the formation of alternative products such as formate esters and
104 formamides.

105

106 **3. Scientific premise and background**

107

108 **CO₂ emissions and formic acid**

109 Combustion of hydrocarbon-containing materials has led to a massive increase in
110 atmospheric CO₂ emissions, with current global atmospheric CO₂ concentrations at 421.47
111 ppm (March 3rd, 2024), and a steadily yearly increase of 2.4 ppm on average since 2012.¹¹
112 There is a pressing need for the development of more sustainable and clean energy concepts,
113 and although in recent years, most efforts to ease CO₂ accumulation have focused on
114 developing new energy efficiency and sequestration technologies,¹² the obvious abundance of
115 this greenhouse gas has also come to represent a readily available, cheap, and renewable source
116 of C1-carbon for producing various value-added chemicals such as formic acid.¹³

117 Molecular hydrogen (H₂) is emerging as a carrier of renewable fuel,¹⁴ but its necessary
118 compression or liquefaction is highly energetically demanding, resulting in a costly and

119 hazardous procedure.¹⁵ Alternatively, formic acid is often touted as a promising H₂ carrier, as
 120 it achieves a higher volumetric density and is liquefied under standard temperatures and
 121 pressures, making its handling more economical and much safer (Fig. 2).¹⁶

122
 123 **Fig. 2** Hydrogen gas presents a hazard for transportation. Instead, formic acid can easily store
 124 hydrogen, facilitating transport, and offering a viable H₂ delivery method. This occurs through a very
 125 convenient hydrogenation-dehydrogenation cycle.

126 For its role as a liquid H₂ carrier, formic acid can be acquired through the catalytic
 127 hydrogenation of CO₂ emissions.¹⁷ In addition to its role as a stabilised form of H₂ fuel, formic
 128 acid is also viewed as an economically valuable platform feedstock for producing numerous
 129 other higher value-added chemicals within the circular bioeconomy (Fig. 3).¹⁸

130
 131 **Fig. 3** The processes involved in formic acid (formate) bioeconomy. Formate can be obtained through
 132 different methods and from different sources, and is ultimately transformed into high-value chemicals
 133 affording huge economic benefits. Given its complexity, it is not possible to develop any new work
 134 into formate bioeconomy without including more than one research discipline, allowing for
 135 multidisciplinary advancements in a reasonably timely manner. This image has been adapted from
 136 Yishai et al. (2016)¹⁸

137 Achieving formic acid production directly from CO₂ and H₂ is a rather challenging
 138 reaction, as it requires expensive catalysts and harsh conditions to yield high conversion
 139 rates.¹⁹⁻²² Thermodynamically speaking, formate formation is favourable at pH = 7 (e.q. 1’);

140 but under standard conditions (pH = 0, eq. 1), under which formic acid is produced, the
 141 equilibrium favours CO₂ formation. This equilibrium, however, is temperature dependent, and
 142 low temperatures favour formic acid production. At 0°C, 50 bar CO₂ and 150 bar H₂, the
 143 maximal formic acid concentration that can be produced is ca. 3 M.²³⁻²⁶

144

147

148 The severity of the reaction conditions can be diminished by using a less energy-
 149 demanding biocatalyst: formate dehydrogenase. So far, there are several reports that the
 150 production of formic acid from CO₂ can proceed enzymatically through FDH, either as a whole
 151 cell biocatalyst or as an immobilised or free enzyme.²⁷⁻³¹ However, with the higher expected
 152 accumulation of formic acid at lower temperatures, FDH will likely be susceptible to protein
 153 denaturation by the ensuing low pH environment and so to maintain its catalytic activity would
 154 require a highly acid stable nature (Fig. 4).

155

156

157 **Fig. 4** Concentrations of dissolved formic acid in equilibrium with CO₂ and hydrogen at different
 158 temperatures. At lower temperatures, the equilibrium favours formic acid formation, which in turn,
 159 creates a more acidic environment. But would require a catalyst that is able to operate at low
 160 temperatures, such as enzymes (FDH).

161

162 **Formate dehydrogenase as a biocatalyst to promote CO₂ reduction**

163 FDH is the biological catalyst responsible for the interconversion between formate and
164 CO₂. Mostly, FDH enzymes evolved to preferentially catalyse the formate oxidation, but some
165 FDHs are reportedly more active in catalysing CO₂ reduction.²⁸

166 FDH is generally regarded as a rather ubiquitous enzyme and it also constitutes a very
167 heterogeneous group of enzymes regarding cellular location and structural organisation.^{32,33}
168 The cellular location of FDH appears to be somewhat related to functional specialisation.³⁴ For
169 example, as formate can act as an energy source in hydrogenotrophic methanogens
170 (*Methanococcus*), cytosolic FDH will facilitate the conversion to CO₂ via the methanogenic
171 pathway.³⁵ On the other hand, in Gram-negative bacteria, membrane-bound periplasmic FDH
172 serves to funnel electrons to the quinone pool in the periplasm, where the generation of protons
173 powers the proton-motive force that enables energy to be conserved.^{36,37} As to structural
174 organisation, there are two separate classes of FDH that have been characterised by the absence
175 or presence of a metal ion in the active site, and which are described in greater detail in the
176 sections below.

177 **Non-metallo FDH.** Non-metallo FDH are commonly observed in aerobic hosts, and so
178 taken to be oxygen tolerant. In microbial cells, they are typically localised to the cytoplasm,
179 while in plant cells they are confined to the mitochondrion.^{38,39} Besides its role as the main
180 energy source in all methylotrophic microbes, the precise physiological role of non-metallo
181 FDH in other hosts remains unclear. Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺), or in some
182 rare instances nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP⁺),⁴⁰ is generally used as
183 the cofactor for the redox catalysis reaction. The forward formate oxidation reaction is typically
184 favoured among non-metallo FDHs; which is consistent with the metabolic role of FDH in the
185 cytoplasm of fermentative microorganisms where it primarily functions to reduce CO₂ for the
186 biosynthesis of C1 compounds,⁴¹ and these enzymes have been frequently used in cofactor
187 recycling for cascade enzymatic reactions.⁴² As a caveat, however, the lower catalytic activity
188 of non-metallo FDH, the prohibitive cost of NAD⁺ and the high lability of NADH in acids, are
189 obvious disadvantages for practical CO₂ reduction applications, and for that reason this class
190 of FDH also tends to be viewed as a less viable option.^{43,44}

191 **Metallo FDH.** By contrast, metallo FDHs exhibit much greater variation based on
192 metal content, subunit composition, quaternary structure, cellular localisation, active-site
193 residues, O₂ sensitivity, and physiological function. True to its name, metallo FDH can contain
194 either molybdenum (Mo) or tungsten (W) within its active site, and thus structurally belongs
195 to the dimethyl sulfoxide reductase family of enzymes.⁴⁵ Although there is still some debate

196 over the precise catalytic mechanism of FDH, it is accepted that the reaction mechanism in
197 metallo FDH can accommodate a range of electron donor-acceptor cofactors, including
198 artificial cofactors.^{45,46-47}

199 In terms of oxygen sensitivity, there are some important differences among metallo
200 FDHs. For instance, selenocysteine (Sec) containing FDHs are without exception highly O₂-
201 sensitive enzymes, but FDHs with an active site cysteine residue can be less prone to oxic
202 inactivation. In addition, those having tungsten tend to always be inactivated by O₂, but those
203 containing molybdenum are more stable against oxygen. FDHs with molybdenum in the active
204 site centre are primarily found amongst prokaryotes, while those with tungsten are largely
205 confined to various extremophilic microorganisms.⁴⁸

206 In the quest to develop novel CO₂ reducing biocatalysts, growing research interest has
207 been drawn to the metallo FDHs. In a head-to-head comparison of turnover activity, metallo
208 FDH clearly outperforms the nonmetal-containing enzyme, making it the far better option for
209 potential applications as a CO₂ reductase. Still, practical sticking points with the metallo FDHs
210 continue to be their poor and difficult recombinant expression in *E. coli*, and their short-lived
211 ability to retain full activity due to O₂ sensitivity. This sensitivity stems from a sulfido ligand
212 bound at the active site,^{49,50} which has been posited as the acceptor of the hydride ion during
213 the redox reaction.⁵¹ Stabilising inhibitors (such as ionic azides and nitrates) are typically used
214 with metallo-FDHs to help reduce the sensitivity to O₂ by blocking O₂ access to the active site
215 and keeping the sulfido ligand in position. However, in the presence of O₂ but absence of
216 inhibitor, the sulfido ligand is immediately replaced by O₂, which brings about enzyme
217 inactivation.⁵²

218

219 **4. Research implementation and impact**

220 In order to accomplish our objectives, we structured the scope of the research project
221 into three work phases (Enzyme Discovery, Enzyme Performance, and Molecular
222 Understanding) to foster the transdisciplinary exchange of scientific ideas and knowledge
223 between consortium members. These three phases, although mostly linear in nature, also
224 provided the opportunity for all members to start working in parallel while waiting for more
225 information and results from the other team members. In this way, each team developed their
226 areas of expertise while updating, complementing and informing the other parts of the
227 consortium. Exceptionally high levels of constant communication were crucial for the
228 advancement of the project.

229 **Enzyme Discovery**

230 Despite the omnipresence of microorganisms in nature, only a small fraction of these
231 can be readily cultured in the laboratory.^{53,54} This leaves most of the genetic potential within
232 these natural microbial populations unexplored when traditional culture-based methods are
233 used. Metagenomics is an effective approach for revealing the untapped reservoir of microbial
234 and genomic biodiversity in various environments.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ The typical metagenomics workflow
235 begins with collecting samples from the subject environment, followed by isolating the DNA.
236 DNA extraction is much less discriminating than cultivation-dependent approaches, allowing
237 for a more comprehensive representation of the collective genome, or ‘metagenome’, of the
238 microbial community in an environmental sample. After isolation, the metagenome is
239 fragmented and then undergoes high-throughput DNA sequencing. Genes encoding possible
240 novel biological functions are identified from the sequence data by computer algorithms
241 comparing with known genes and proteins (Fig. 5).

243 **Fig. 5** Schematic of a typical metagenomics workflow. DNA is extracted from selected samples and
244 sequenced. The raw sequence data is analysed and the genes of interest are identified, allowing for
245 their synthesis, transformation and expression under the required laboratory conditions. The workflow
246 leads to further experimental procedures for enzymatic molecular understanding.

247 In order to discover FDH biocatalysts that are naturally cold adapted and highly acid-
248 tolerant, the researchers at VTT conducted a comprehensive metagenomics survey of the
249 microbial communities in two acidic environments. By selecting an environment that is both
250 sufficiently unique and extreme, and, most importantly, that also reflects the sought-after
251 properties of the enzyme we aimed to significantly expand the overall gene pool and thereby
252 enhance the possibility of discovering FDH enzymes with the desired physical and catalytic
253 properties that were hereto unknown.

254 The metagenomic approach considerably expanded the available gene pool, yielding to
255 the discovery of novel FDH genes, encoding both metallo and non-metallo FDHs. These
256 newly-identified genes represent a wide diversity of microorganisms, as well as enzyme
257 structures and cellular locations, supporting our aim to cover as much functional diversity as
258 possible.

259

260 **Protein production and enzymatic performance**

261 In continuation to the metagenomic analysis, these new metal-containing FDHs were
262 explored for their potential to act as stable catalysts that can convert CO₂ and H₂ to formic acid
263 for industrial applications. Different *fdh* genes were selected from the novel FDH gene pool; a
264 selection made to represent as wide a protein level and taxonomic level as possible. In this way,
265 it could be established which of the discovered variants could be expressed for activity
266 screening.

267 Overexpression of the enzymes was designed to test different plasmids, vectors,
268 expression conditions and genetic modifications.⁵⁸⁻⁶² Given that the extremophiles in this study
269 were derived from cold and acidic environments, their enzymatic activity was tested at different
270 pHs and temperatures.

271 In order to address and circumvent the linearity of the project, parallel work involving
272 other oxygen-sensitive, metal-dependent FDHs was developed to study the enzymatic active
273 site and how its modification affects enzyme performance. At this stage, most of the
274 experimental work was carried out with a formate dehydrogenase from *E. coli* K12, following
275 Li's protocol.^{62,63-66}

276 The procedure is outlined in Fig. 6. A key aspect of the analytical work was to establish the
277 activity of these enzymes with artificial electron donors, such as methyl and benzyl viologens.
278 These compounds afforded an efficient method for measuring enzymatic activities, given their
279 unique colorimetric properties.^{67,68}

280

281 **Fig. 6** After the metagenomic workflow showed in Fig. 5, a different skill set is needed. This figure
282 displays a protein engineering procedure, starting with a PCR (for protein engineering through DNA

283 mutations) and ending with activity assays. Most of the procedure needs to be carried out inside an
284 anaerobic chamber. The enhanced mutations selected through the activity assays can then be used to
285 expand the synthetic scope, serving as a bridge between the metagenomics field and the organic
286 synthetic chemistry area.

287 At the time this article was written, only modification through rational design was
288 attempted. However, we believe that best results will be obtained through a combination of
289 both directed evolution and rational design. Ideally, if more time was granted, an in-depth study
290 comparing these two parallel lines of work (enzymes from metagenome analysis and available
291 enzymes) would be carried out to extract the precious information. As we stand, those avenues
292 of investigation might have to be saved for future endeavours.

293

294 **Molecular understanding and catalytic applications:**

295 This phase of the project delivered what might be perceived as the most practical results
296 in terms of CO₂ capture and chemical transformation, since it focused on the optimisation of
297 biocatalysis to extend the synthetic product scope.

298 To date, most large-scale efforts have centred around the conversion of CO₂ to small
299 molecules of high commercial value. Two strong contenders in these processes are methanol
300 and ethanol, which can be easily used as a fuels, as a precursors for more complex fuels or as
301 a building blocks towards other valuable chemicals.⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ Nowadays, most of the CO₂ is used
302 for fertilisers in the agrochemical industry through urea manufacture.^{72,73}

303 In chemical terms, carbon dioxide is a rather stable, electrophilic molecule. Contrary to
304 what might be expected, it is, nonetheless, quick to react with basic compounds;⁷⁴ or with
305 highly reactive substrates or under harsh conditions.⁷⁵ Milder chemical methods continue to be
306 developed.⁷⁶ In terms of biocatalysis, three common enzymes are used in the incorporation of
307 carbon dioxide: carbonic anhydrase for the formation of hydrogen carbonate, RuBisCO in the
308 photosynthetic pathway and formate dehydrogenase to obtain formate.⁷⁷

309 It is the latter option that was taken as a stepping-stone to delve into the biocatalysis-
310 synthetic organic chemistry interface. Thus far, the use of FDH to produce compounds other
311 than formate has been practically nonexistent, besides the non-natural reduction of nitrate to
312 nitrite reported by Hartmann et al, and the formic ester cleavage introduced by Frölich.^{78,79}
313 Given that amines show a strong affinity for electrophiles - including CO₂,^{80,81} the prospect of
314 formylation reactions of amines through FDH was explored. In this way, we hoped to combine
315 disciplines to achieve a wider range of substrates for FDH for the direct synthesis of interesting

316 organic compounds and to provide a milder alternative to conventional carbon dioxide trapping
317 methods (Fig. 7).

318

319

320 **Fig. 7** Carbon dioxide sequestration through formate dehydrogenase to obtain a range of valuable
321 chemicals. Nowadays the excessive amounts of atmospheric CO₂ constitute a threat to society. By
322 using biocatalytic methods to transform those harmful greenhouse gases into valuable chemicals
323 would constitute a rather elegant and efficient solution to the problem

324 The production of C1-derived platform chemicals for the development of new amides
325 would not have been possible - or would have been much slower - if not for the combination
326 of knowledge on enzyme promiscuity, enzyme engineering and synthetic organic chemistry.
327 Once again, the inherent value of the consortium approach and its different skill sets is brought
328 back to the limelight. Through the collaboration, it became possible to not only focus on the
329 discovery and development of new CO₂-fixating FDHs (a relevant aim on its own), but we
330 could also delve further into the synthetic value of CO₂ in chemistry. At the same time, the
331 linearity of the project did also play a part in the slow deliverance of results from all parts. With
332 more time, the overall benefits of the consortium would easily exceed the downsides, which
333 for this case, were mostly schedule-based.

334

335 5. The Consortium Approach: Lessons Learned

336 In view of our experience, we would like to present this perspective as a case study for
337 the benefits, and drawbacks, of working in the highly collaborative environment that ensued
338 the creation of the project. Besides the success of producing novel FDHs and sustainable new

339 methods for formic acid biosynthesis, the most valuable outcome was the considerable personal
340 and professional growth experienced. Each partner was able to do individual research, and
341 results were enhanced by the overarching input from the network.

342 This multidisciplinary environment fostered the development of transferable skills;
343 such as team working, presentation and communication skills. In this way, monthly meetings
344 and work presentations were supplemented with a well-established knowledge transfer scheme:
345 from bachelor students to principal investigators, everyone was willing to offer their unique
346 perspective on the project, and to share their unique set of skills.

347 While communication throughout the programme was always present and abundant,
348 the much-needed multidisciplinary approach was, however, demanding. The whole project was
349 much more ambitious than initially expected, and in reality, working together was not always
350 possible. The physical separation constituted a clear disadvantage for building active
351 connections amongst the researchers. Additionally, each round of the project required learning
352 cycles from all its members, along with good doses of willingness and the ability to reach out.
353 The challenging nature of the project marked its fast-learning rhythm: a hectic pace that was
354 only made bearable by the constant help and support from all the network members.

355 At the same time, the intrinsic nature of ExtremoForm translated into a linear timeline:
356 the results from the metagenomic analysis were needed for the enzyme performance assays,
357 which were needed for the development of the molecular understanding phase. Contingency
358 measures were applied, such as working with readily-available enzymes, but they do not
359 distract from the fact that time was a very important factor and that it was very clearly
360 insufficient.

361 With regards to time, the most glaringly obvious issue was the 2020 coronavirus
362 pandemic. While perhaps consortia in other fields have a wider choice of workplace,
363 (bio)chemistry is very limited on the possibilities for remote work. Unfortunately, the
364 pandemic severely hindered our ability to work in situ, especially during the lockdown stage,
365 meaning that most experiments got a considerable delay from the original plan. Not only that,
366 but working in shifts meant that direct communication with other teams was severed, and we
367 relied mainly on the digital approach – often a lot more convoluted than needs be. The long
368 time that took to get back to in-person meetings was another setback. However, in spite of all
369 the difficulties, we can say that through collaboration and learning, we have delivered some
370 outstanding research, the results of which we hope will be published separately.

371 In addition, ExtremoForm also allowed for the development of different branches of
372 work, including two master theses, undergraduate-level participation and bachelor projects.

373 The massive amounts of data produced, not directly related to the original project, can be used
374 in the future, especially focusing on IA development of new methods, closing the cycle and
375 starting a new iteration (Fig. 1).

376 Clearly, ExtremoForm presented a project that was exponentially more complex than
377 initially thought, mainly due to the fact that biology is rather less predictable than chemistry.
378 Not only is it not a guarantee that a metagenomic analysis will produce a good match for what
379 is needed, but even if it does, it is a very plausible possibility that it is not feasible to translate
380 the findings into a real laboratory setting. For this reason, we believe that these difficult
381 endeavours should be taken step-wise, from easy to difficult, and taking time to focus on
382 learning cycles, allowing for the ambition to produce its fruit. Despite the hardship, one thing
383 has become apparent: forming a consortium has always been advantageous. In this sense, the
384 implementation of collaborations on a practical level - as opposed to the more theoretical
385 networking approach prevalent in conferences and other sporadic encounters - leads to more
386 grounded science. We now know how each member works, which will no doubt be of benefit
387 in future challenges.

388 Nowadays, all funding agencies, individual researchers and academic institutions are
389 all pointing towards an undeniable reality: an isolated researcher will never accomplish as
390 much as someone who is in touch with different experts, from different fields, promoting an
391 open, and constructive, communication of science. And while perhaps not everyone has the
392 opportunity to form an official bond (i.e., funded consortium) with other fields, collaboration -
393 official or unofficial - should always be encouraged. By merging our different skills, it was
394 possible to create a more complete, and thus realistic, picture of a very complex plan, and has
395 led to high quality -albeit incomplete at this stage- science.

396

397 **Acknowledgements**

398 This research has received financial support from the Research Council of Finland in the form
399 of the ExtremoForm project granted to M.B., S.S. and J.D. (Decision no 329510). We thank
400 Dr. Heidi Henrikson for helpful discussions.

401

402 **References**

403 ¹ P. Friedlingstein, M. O'Sullivan, M. W. Jones, R. M. Andrew, D. C. E. Bakker, J. Hauck, P.
404 Landschützer, C. Le Quéré, I. T. Lujikx, G. P. Peters, W. Peters, J. Pongratz, C. Schwingshackl,
405 S. Sitch, J. G. Canadell, P. Ciais, R. B. Jackson, S. R. Alin, P. Anthoni, L. Barbero, N. R. Bates,
406 M. Becker, N. Bellouin, B. Decharme, L. Bopp, I. B. Mandhara Brasika, P. Cadule, M. A.

407 Chamberlain, N. Chandra, T.-T.-T. Chau, F. Chevallier, L. P. Chini, M. Cronin, X. Dou, K.
408 Enyo, W. Evans, S. Falk, R. A. Feely, L. Feng, D. J. Ford, T. Gasser, J. Ghattas, T. Gkritzalis,
409 G. Grassi, L. Gregor, N. Gruber, Ö. Gürses, I. Harris, M. Hefner, J. Heinke, R. A. Houghton,
410 G. C. Hurtt, Y. Iida, T. Ilyina, A. R. Jacobson, A. Jain, T. Jarníková, A. Jersild, F. Jiang, Z. Jin,
411 F. Joos, E. Kato, R. F. Keeling, D. Kennedy, K. Klein Goldewijk, J. Knauer, J. I. Korsbakken,
412 A. Körtzinger, X. Lan, N. Lefèvre, H. Li, J. Liu, Z. Liu, L. Ma, G. Marland, N. Mayot, P. C.
413 McGuire, G. A. McKinley, G. Meyer, E. J. Morgan, D. R. Munro, S.-I. Nakaoka, Y. Niwa, K.
414 M. O'Brien, A. Olsen, A. M. Omar, T. Ono, M. Paulsen, D. Pierrot, K. Pocock, B. Poulter, C.
415 M. Powis, G. Rehder, L. Resplandy, E. Robertson, C. Rödenbeck, T. M. Rosan, J. Schwinger,
416 R. Séférian, T. L. Smallman, S. M. Smith, R. Sospedra-Alfonso, Q. Sun, A. J. Sutton, C.
417 Sweeney, S. Takao, P. P. Tans, H. Tian, B. Tilbrook, H. Tsujino, F. Tubiello, G. R. van der
418 Werf, E. van Ooijen, R. Wanninkhof, M. Watanabe, C. Wimart-Rousseau, D. Yang, X. Yang,
419 W. Yuan, X. Yue, S. Zaehle, J. Zeng, B. Zheng; Global Carbon Budget 2023, *Earth Syst. Sci.*
420 *Data*, 15, 5301.

421 ²K. Miyazaki, K. Bowman; *Nat. Comm.* **2023**, 14, 1604.

422 ³S. Bierbaumer, M. Nattermann, L. Schulz, R. Zschoche, T. J. Erb, C. K. Winkler, M. Tinzl,
423 S. M. Glueck; *Chem. Rev.* **2023**, 123, 5702.

424 ⁴G. Tcherkez, A. M. Limami; *New Phytol.* **2019**, 223, 2, 520.

425 ⁵D. Archer, M. R. Ashmore, O. Aumont, D. Baker, M. Battle, M. Bender, L. P. Bopp, P.
426 Bousquet, K. Caldeira, P. Ciais, P. M. Cox, W. Cramer, F. Dentener, I. G. Enting, C. B. Field,
427 P. Friedlingstein, E. A. Holland, R. A. Houghton, J. I. House, A. Ishida, A. K. Jain, I. A.
428 Janssens, F. Joos, T. Kaminski, C. D. Keeling, R. F. Keeling, D. W. Kicklighter, K. E. Kohfeld,
429 W. Knorr, R. Law, T. Lenton, K. Lindsay, E. Maier-Reimer, A. C. Manning, R. J. Matear, A.
430 D. McGuire, J. M. Melillo, R. Meyer, M. Mund, J. C. Orr, S. Piper, K. Plattner, P. J. Rayner,
431 S. Sitch, R. Slater, S. Taguchi, P. P. Tans, H. Q. Tian, M. F. Weiring, T. Whorf, A. Yool, G.
432 D. Farquhar, M. J. R. Fasham, M. L. Goulden, M. Heimann, V. J. Jaramillo, H. S. Kheshgi, C.
433 Lé Quéré, R. J. Scholes, D. W. R. Wallace, I. C. Prentice; The Carbon Cycle and Atmospheric
434 Carbon Dioxide, Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
435 (<https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/TAR-03.pdf>)

436 ⁶D. Wei, R. Sang, P. Sponholz, H. Junge, M. Beller; *Nature Energy*, **2022**, 7, 438.

437 ⁷M. Z. do Valle Gomes, G. Masdeu, P. Eiring, A. Kuhlemann, M. Sauer, B. Åkerman, A. E.
438 C. Palmqvist; *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **2021**, 11, 6952.

439 ⁸A. M. Klibanov, B. N. Alberti, S. E. Zale; *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **1982**, 24, 25.

440 ⁹ H. Chen, Y. Huang, C. Sha, J. M. Moradian, Y.-C. Yong, Z. Fang; *Renew. Sustain. Energy*
441 *Rev.* **2023**, *178*, 113270.

442 ¹⁰ Research Council of Finland, C1 Value Academy Programme.
443 [https://www.aka.fi/en/research-funding/programmes-and-other-funding-schemes/academy-](https://www.aka.fi/en/research-funding/programmes-and-other-funding-schemes/academy-programmes/alaisivut/academy-programmes-under-evaluation/c1-value-20202023/)
444 [programmes/alaisivut/academy-programmes-under-evaluation/c1-value-20202023/](https://www.aka.fi/en/research-funding/programmes-and-other-funding-schemes/academy-programmes/alaisivut/academy-programmes-under-evaluation/c1-value-20202023/)

445 ¹¹ X. Lan, P. Tans, K. W. Thoning; Trends in globally-averaged CO₂ determined from NOAA
446 Global Monitoring Laboratory measurements. Version 2024-02.
447 <https://doi.org/10.15138/9N0H-ZH07> Data accessed on 5th March 2024.

448 ¹² H. McLaughlin, A. A. Littlefield, M. Menefee, A. Kinzer, T. Hull, B. K. Sovacool, M. D.
449 Bazilian, J. Kim, S. Griffiths; *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2023**, *177*, 113215.

450 ¹³ A. Satanowski, A. Bar-Even; *EMBO reports*, **2020**, *21*, e50273.

451 ¹⁴ Q. Hassan, I. D. J. Azzawi, A. Z. Sameen, H. M. Salman; *Sustainability*, **2023**, *15*, 11501.

452 ¹⁵ Y. Kojima; *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, **2019**, *44*, *33*, 18179.

453 ¹⁶ C. Kim, Y. Lee, K. Kim; *Energies*, **2023**, *16*, *6*, 2613.

454 ¹⁷ J. J. Carroll, J. D. Slupsky, A. E. Mather; *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*, **1991**, *210*, *6*, 1201.

455 ¹⁸ O. Yishai, S. N. Lindner, J. Gonzalez de la Cruz, H. Tenenboim, A. Bar-Even; *Curr. Op.*
456 *Chem. Biol.* **2016**, *35*, 1.

457 ¹⁹ C. Hao, S. Wang, M. Li, L. Kang, X. Ma; *Catal. Today*, **2011**, *160*, *1*, 184.

458 ²⁰ C.-S. He, L. Gong, J. Zhang, P.-P. He, Y. Mu; *J. CO₂ Util.* **2017**, *19*, 157.

459 ²¹ Y. Himeda, S. Miyazawa, T. Hirose; *ChemSusChem*, **2011**, *4*, *4*, 487.

460 ²² A. Weilhard, M. I. Qadir, V. Sans, J. Dupont; *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, *3*, 1628.

461 ²³ G. Pietricola, C. Ottone, D. Fino, T. Tommasi; *J. CO₂ Util.* **2020**, *42*, 101343.

462 ²⁴ S. Moret, P. J. Dyson, G. Laurenczy; *Nat. Comm.* **2014**, *5*, 4017.

463 ²⁵ J. C. Boyington, V. N. Gladyshev, S. V. Khangulov, T. C. Stadtman, P. D. Sun; *Science*,
464 **1997**, *275*, *5304*, 1305.

465 ²⁶ A. Sharma, Y. Kawarabayasi, T. Satyanarayana; *Extremophiles*, **2012**, *16*, 1.

466 ²⁷ L. Calzadiaz-Ramirez, A. S. Meyer; *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2022**, *73*, 95.

467 ²⁸ R. Miyatani, Y. Amao, *J. Mol. Catal. B: Enzymatic*, **2004**, *27*, *2-3*, 121.

468 ²⁹ Z. Zhang, T. Vasiliu, F. Li, A. Laaksonen, F. Mocchi, X. Ji; *J. CO₂ Util.* **2021**, *52*, 101679.

469 ³⁰ Y. Amao, *J. CO₂ Util.* **2018**, *26*, 623.

470 ³¹ H. Choe, J. C. Joo, D. H. Cho, M. H. Kim, S. H. Lee, K. D. Jung, Y. H. Kim; *PLOS One*,
471 **2014**, *9*, *7*, e103111.

472 ³² M. Jormakka, B. Byrne, S. Iwata; *Curr. Op. Struct. Biol.* **2003**, *13*, *4*, 418.

473 ³³ C. F. Nielsen, L. Lange, A. S. Meyer; *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2019**, *37*, *5*, 107408.

474 ³⁴ B. R. Crable, C. M. Plugge, M. J. McInerney, A. J. M. Stams; *Enzyme Res.* **2011**, *1*, 532536.
475 ³⁵ U. Deppenmeier; *Prog. Nucleic Acid Res.* **2002**, *71*, 223.
476 ³⁶ C. E. Price, A. J. Driessen; *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Mol. Cell Res.* **2010**, 1803, 6, 748.
477 ³⁷ H. Wang, R. P. Gunsalus; *J. Bacteriol.* **2003**, 185, *17*, 5076.
478 ³⁸ A. A. Alekseeva, S. S. Savin, V. I. Tishkov; *Acta Naturae*, **2011**, *3*, *4*, 38.
479 ³⁹ V. I. Tishkov, V. O. Popov; *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, **2004**, *69*, *11*, 1252.
480 ⁴⁰ L. Calzadiaz-Ramirez, C. Calvó-Tusell, G. M. M. Stoffel, S. N. Lindner, S. Osuna, T. J. Erb,
481 M. García-Borràs, A. Bar-Even, C. G. Acevedo-Rocha; *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10*, *14*, 7512.
482 ⁴¹ M. Takacs, O. V. Makhlynets, P. L. Tolbert, I. V. Korendovych; *Protein Eng. Des. Sel.* **2017**,
483 *30*, *3*, 279.
484 ⁴² V. I. Tishkov, V. O. Popov; *Biomol. Eng.* **2006**, *23*, 89.
485 ⁴³ C. A. R. Cotton, C. Edlich-Muth, A. Bar-Even; *Curr. Op. Biotechnol.* **2018**, *49*, 49.
486 ⁴⁴ M. Talvitie, Acid-tolerant enzymes and their biotechnical application in CO₂ fixation,
487 Bachelor Thesis, Aalto Yliopisto, **2020**.
488 ⁴⁵ H. C. A. Raaijmakers, M. J. Romão; *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.* **2006**, *11*, *7*, 849.
489 ⁴⁶ R. Hille, J. Hall, P. Basu; *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, *7*, 3963.
490 ⁴⁷ H. Kumar, M. Khosraneh, S. S. M. Bandaru, C. Schulzke, S. Leimkühler; *Molecules*, **2023**,
491 *28*, 1537.
492 ⁴⁸ F. A. M. de Bok, P.-L. Hagedoorn, P. J. Silva, W. R. Hagen, E. Schiltz, K. Firtsche, A. J. M.
493 Stams; *Eur. J. Biochem.* **2003**, *270*, 2476.
494 ⁴⁹ P. Kaufmann, B. R. Duffus, B. Mitrova, C. Iobbi-Nivol, C. Teutloff, M. Nimtz, L. Jansch,
495 U. Wollenberger, S. Leimkühler; *Biochemistry*, **2018**, *57*, *7*, 1130.
496 ⁵⁰ S. Reschke, B. R. Duffus, P. Schrapers, S. Mebs, C. Teutloff, H. Dau, M. Haumann, S.
497 Leimkühler; *Biochemistry*, **2019**, *58*, *17*, 2228.
498 ⁵¹ D. Niks, J. Duvvuru, M. Escalona, R. Hille; *J. Biol. Chem.* **2016**, *291*, *3*, 1162.
499 ⁵² K. Laun, B. R. Duffus, S. Wahlefeld, S. Katz, D. Belger, P. Hildebrandt, M. A. Mroginski,
500 S. Leimkühler, I. Zebger; *Chem. Eur. J.* **2022**, *28*, e202201091.
501 ⁵³ K. Lewis, S. Epstein, A. D'Onofrio, L. L. Ling; *J. Antibiot.* **2010**, *63*, 468.
502 ⁵⁴ E. J. Stewart; *J. Bacteriol.* **2012**, *194*, *16*, 4151.
503 ⁵⁵ N. N. Nam, H. D. K. Do, K. T. L. Trinh, N. Y. Lee; *Foods*, **2023**, *12*, *11*, 2140.
504 ⁵⁶ E. P. Culligan, R. D. Sleator, J. R. Marchesi, C. Hill; *Virulence*, **2014**, *5*, *3*, 399.
505 ⁵⁷ R. Li, Y. Wang, H. Hu, Y. Tan, Y. Ma; *Nat. Comm.* **2022**, *13*, 7978.
506 ⁵⁸ C. Pinske, M. Bonn, S. Kruger, U. Lindenstrauss, R. G. Sawers; *PLoS One*, **2011**, *6*, *8*,
507 e22830.

508 ⁵⁹ C. Pinske; *Front. Microbiol.* **2018**, *9*, 1238.

509 ⁶⁰ S. Sahin, R. Cai, R. D. Milton, S. Abdellaoui, F. C. Macazo, S. D. Minteer; *J. Electrochem.*
510 *Soc.* **2018**, *165*, *3*, H109.

511 ⁶¹ H. Stamatis; *Multienzymatic Assemblies: Methods and Protocols (Methods in Molecular*
512 *Biology)*, Springer US: Humana, 1st Ed. **2022**.

513 ⁶² F. Li, S. Scheller, M. Lienemann; *J. CO₂ Util.* **2023**, *77*, 102608.

514 ⁶³ R. R. Jameson, A. M. Diamond; *RNA*, **2004**, *10*, *7*, 1142.

515 ⁶⁴ M. J. Axley, D. A. Grahame, T. C. Stadtman; *J. Biol. Chem.* **1990**, *265*, *30*, 18213.

516 ⁶⁵ T. C. Stadtman, J. N. Davis, W. M. Ching, F. Zinoni, A. Böck; *Biofactors*, **1991**, *3*, *1*, 21.

517 ⁶⁶ E. Seol, Y. Jang, S. Kim, Y.-K. Oh, S. Park; *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy*, **2012**, *37*, 15045.

518 ⁶⁷ S. Ikeyama, Y. Amao; *Chem. Cat. Chem.* **2017**, *9*, *5*, 833.

519 ⁶⁸ S. Ikeyama, T. Katagiri, Y. Amao; *J. Photochem. Photobiol., A*, **2018**, *358*, 362.

520 ⁶⁹ D. S. Marlin, E. Sarron, Ó. Sigurbjörnsson, *Front. Chem.* **2018**, *6*:446.

521 ⁷⁰ S. K. Kuk, R. K. Singh, D. H. Nam, R. Singh, J.-K. Lee, C. B. Park; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*,
522 **2017**, *56*, 3827.

523 ⁷¹ X. Wang, P. J. Ramírez, W. Liao, J. A. Rodriguez, P. Liu; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, *33*,
524 13103.

525 ⁷² J. G. Driver, R. E. Owen, T. Makanyire, J. A. Lake, J. McGregor, P. Styring; *Front. Energy*
526 *Res.* **2019**, *7*:88.

527 ⁷³ J. Ding, R. Ye, Y. Fu, Y. He, Y. Wu, Y. Zhang, Q. Zhong, H. H. Kun, M. Fan; *Nat. Comm.*
528 **2023**, *14*, 4586.

529 ⁷⁴ T. Sakakura, K. Kohno; *Chem. Commun.* **2009**, *11*, 1312.

530 ⁷⁵ Q. Liu, L. Wu, R. Jackstell, M. Beller; *Nat. Comm.* **2015**, *6*, 5933.

531 ⁷⁶ M. Franz, T. Stalling, H. Steinert, J. Martens; *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, **2018**, *16*, 8292.

532 ⁷⁷ R. Villa, S. Nieto, A. Donaire, P. Lozano, *Molecules*, **2023**, *28*, 5520.

533 ⁷⁸ P. Fröhlich, K. Albert, M. Bertau; *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2011**, *9*, 7941.

534 ⁷⁹ T. Hartmann, N. Schwanhold, S. Leimkühler; *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Proteins Proteomics*,
535 **2015**, *1854*, *9*, 1090.

536 ⁸⁰ J. Vaitla, Y. Guttormsen, J. K. Mannisto, A. Nova, T. Repo, A. Bayer, K. H. Hopmann, *ACS*
537 *Catal.* **2017**, *7*, 7231.

538 ⁸¹ T. Niemi, T. Repo, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2019**, 1180.